

RESTORING VISION IN MYOPIA WITH AYURVEDIC INTERVENTION – A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Timira is the disease mentioned under *Dristigata Rogas* in our literature. The disease is progressive in nature i.e if timely untreated, can lead to *Kacha* and potentially even *Linghanasha* (loss of vision). In modern ophthalmology *Timira* can be compared with refractive errors like Myopia, Hypermetropia and Astigmatism. **Materials and methods:** A 12 years old male paediatric patient with the complaints of difficulty in clearly seeing distant objects with associated complaints of eye strain, itching and headache since 2 years. An *Ayurvedic Kriyakalpa* therapies like *Seka* and *Tarpana* along with internal medications *Saptamrita Lauha* and *Mahatriphala Grutha* was administered. **Results:** The results showed significant improvement in the vision and other associated complaints of the patient. **Conclusion:** *Ayurvedic* treatment approach thus acts as both curative and preventive.

KEYWORDS: *Timira, Kriyakalpa, Seka, Tarpana, Shamanaoushadis.*

INTRODUCTION

Myopia or shortsightedness is a type of refractive error in which parallel rays of light coming from infinity are focused in front of retina when accommodation is at rest.^[1] The etiological factors contributing myopia are genetic predispose, excessive near work, limited outdoor activity.^[2] The symptoms of simple myopia include poor vision for distance, asthenopic symptoms, half shutting of the eyes.^[3] The diagnosis is confirmed by refraction and treatment suggest prescribing of concave lenses and surgery.^[4]

Myopia is a rapidly growing public health concern globally, with a prediction of 50% of the world population will be myopic by 2050.^[5] In India, among the urban school aged children the prevalence rates rising from 4-8% to over 20% in recent decades.^[6] The rising prevalence of myopia may lead to other ocular complications. Therefore early detection and early intervention are crucial to reduce both the progression of myopia and its associated complications.

In *Ayurveda Dristigata Rogas*^[7] describes eye diseases associated with vision loss. *Timira*^[8] refers to a condition characterized by gradual visual loss, often described as a

sense of darkness, which ultimately result in blindness if untreated. *Timira*, *Kacha* and *Linganasha*^[9] are considered as progressive stages of vision loss. According to *Astanga Hridaya* the *Samanya Timira Chikitsa*^[10] is *Gruthapana, Nasya, Kriyakalpas, Siravyadha* and *Murdhabasti*.

A CASE STUDY

A 12years old male paediatric patient presented with the complaints of difficulty in seeing clearly distant objects with associated complaints of eye strain, itching of both eyes and headache since 2years.

History of present illness

A 12 years male patient presented with the complaints of difficulty in seeing clearly distant objects with associated complaints of eye strain, itching of both eyes and headache since 2 years. A year ago he had consulted an ophthalmologist, diagnosed as myopia and was prescribed spectacles. The patient could not find satisfactory improvement with the spectacles and hence he approached to our OPD.

Family history –Father is astigmatic.

Surgical history – Nothing significant.

Personal History

- Bowel – Once a day
- Appetite – Good
- Micturition – 5-6times a day
- Sleep – Sound
- Diet – Mixed diet

General physical examination

- Blood pressure – 110/70mmHg
- Respiratory rate – 20/min
- Temperature – 98°F
- Pallor – Absent
- Icterus – Absent
- Lymphadenopathy – Not palpable

Asthasthana Pareeksha

- *Nadi* – *Vata-Kaphaja*
- *Mutra* – *Anavilam*
- *Mala* – *Abhadha*
- *Jihwa* – *Alipta*
- *Shabdha* – *Prakruta*
- *Sparsha* – *Sheeta*
- *Drik- Vaikruta*
- *Aakriti* – *Madhyama*

Systemic examination

- Cardiovascular system- NAD
- Respiratory system – NAD
- Gastrointestinal system – NAD
- Central Nervous system – NAD

OCULAR EXAMINATION

On torch and slit-lamp biomicroscopic examinations the ocular structures – eyebrows, eyelashes, eyelids, conjunctiva, sclera, cornea, pupil and lens were bilaterally normal.

Visual acuity examination

Table No -01

Parameters	Right eye	Left eye
VA for Distance Snellen's unaided	6/24	6/36
BCVA	6/6	6/6
Pinhole improvement	6/12	6/24
VA for Near Jaegers	N6	N6

Fundus examination – Normal

Nidana Panchaka-

- *Nidana* – *Mithyachara* (increased screen time, late night awakening)
- *Poorvaroopa* – *Vihwala Drusti* (Blurriness of vision)
- *Roopa* – *Vihwala Drusti* (Blurriness of vision), eye strain, itching of eyes

- *Upashaya* – *Nidra*, reduced screen time, eye exercises
- *Samprapti*

Nidana sevana Mithyachara (increased screen time, late night awakening)

Vitiating of *Tridoshas* predominantly *Vata* and *Pitta*

Vimarga Gamana of these vitiating *Doshas* through *Siras*

Sthanasamshraya in *Patalas* of *Drusti Mandala*

Avyakta Lakshana

- *Samprapti Ghataka*
- *Dosha - Tridosha*
- *Pitta - Alochaka*
- *Kapha - Tarpaka*
- *Vata - Prana and Udana*
- *Dushya - Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa*
- *Adhithana - Prathama Patala*
- *Agni - Jatharagni*
- *Srotas - Rasavaha and Majjavaha*
- *Srotodushiti - Sanga and Vimarggamana*

Diagnosis – *Prathama Patalagata Timira* (Myopia)

Treatment

1. *Netraseka* with *Yastimadhu Churna* and *Triphala Churna Kashaya* for 3days
2. *Tarpana* with *Mahatriphala Gruta^[11]* for 7days

Shamanushadis (Internal medications)-

1. *Tab Saptamrita Lauha^[12]* – 1 tablet twice a day with 2gms of honey after food
2. *Go Grutha* – 1tsp twice a day with warm milk

RESULTS

Visual acuity examination

Table- 02.

Parameters	Right eye	Left eye
VA for Distance Snellen's	6/18	6/24
BCVA	6/6	6/6
Pinhole improvement	6/9	6/12
VA for Near Jaegers	N6	N6

DISCUSSION

Prathama Patalagata Timira is the disorder which is caused by vitiating of *Doshas* in the *Prathama Patala* of the eye. The only symptom explained in *Prathama Patalagata Timira* is *Avyakta Darshana*.

The treatment modality in the present case adopted was *Seka* followed by *Tarpana* and internal medications.

Seka was administered as it helps to eliminate the *Ama* from the *Netra* and improves the circulation, thereby increases the rate of drug absorption.

Triphala has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties and helps balances the *Tridoshas*. *Yastimadhu* is *Pittahara* and *Vatahara*, and also possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory property.

The word *Tarpana* itself indicates nourishment and is also known as *Netra Basti*. This procedure strengthen the ocular and periocular structures of the eyeball. *Mahathriphala Ghruta* is *Vata Pitta Shamaka* and *Chakshushya*. The corneal epithelium and endothelium are lipid permeable are lipid permeable i.e., lipophilic while the stromal layer is hydrophilic. Therefore, both lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs are effectively delivered to cornea. The drug permeability across the sclera depends upon the molecular size and weight of the drug.

Grutha is rich in Vit A, D, E, K and carotene. Vit A and K are antioxidants they help to nourish the outer layer of the eyeball.

Saptamrita Lauha contains *Haritaki*, *Vibhitaki*, *Amalaki*, *Yastimadhu*, *Madhu*, *Grutha* and *Loha Bhasma*. It is acts as *Tridosahara* and *Chakushya*.

Gogrutha acts as *Rasayana*, it nourishes the *Saptadhatu*s, *ojas* and functions as *Indriyaprasadana*. Hence it was adopted as internal medication along with *Saptamrita Lauha*.

CONCLUSION

Eye is sense organ of vision, *Acharya Vagbhata* states that protecting our eyes from disease is the prime duty of every individual, because for a blind person, day and night are the same regardless of wealth. *Ayurveda* emphasizes *Swastasya Swasta Rakshanam*, therefore as a preventive aspect one should avoid the causative factors eye diseases.

In the present era of increasing myopia incidence early diagnosis and treatment are crucial. *Ayurveda* offers treatment modalities like *Netra Kriyakalpas* which are beneficial for both curative and preventive management of the disease. Hence a holistic approach along with eye exercises may be beneficial for better vision.

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